

EMERGE

Equipping Minoritized and
Emerging Research Institutions
to Grow Their Enterprises

Finding Funding: Strategies and Tools for Your Search

A peer-reviewed EMERGE resource from the NORDP
Consultants Program

By: Lauren Aerni-Flessner, Heather Abbott, and Rachel Wallace
Funding by the National Science Foundation, Office of Integrative
Activities (Award No. 2331578)

About the NORDP Consultants Program

The NORDP Consultants Program is dedicated to increasing the diversity of the national research ecosystem by providing research development services to minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) at no cost to the institution.

The program pairs research development professionals with investigators and research leadership to:

1. Strengthen researchers' capacity to compete for external funding,
2. Enhance research enterprise infrastructure and capacity,
3. Inspire institutional research cultures, and
4. Magnify the visibility and competitive reputation of MSIs and ERIs in the research enterprise.

Executive Summary

Many research projects require extramural funding and institutional support to procure the necessary resources to succeed. However, it can be challenging to identify sources of funding, especially for early career researchers and researchers in academic environments where securing external funding is not necessarily an expectation. Therefore, it's important to develop a strong approach for searching for funding. This knowledge article will help you develop a strategy for finding funding and discuss best practices for searching for funding opportunities. The accompanying article 'Is This the Right Fit? Evaluating Funding Opportunities for Your Research' (1) will build on this article to help you identify how well a particular funding opportunity fits your project. Once you have identified a funding opportunity to pursue, the "Reaching Out: Best Practices for Contacting Program Officer" article (2) will help you build skills to engage with sponsors about your research interests.

Target Audience

Primary audience: Investigators seeking external funding for their research, scholarship, and creative artistry.

Secondary audience: This article also serves as a resource for research development and research administration professionals who are new to assisting investigators with finding external funding opportunities.

Suggested Citation: Aerni-Flessner, L., Abbott, H., and Wallace, R. (2025). Finding Funding: Strategies and Tools for Your Search. The NORDP Consultants Program. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16540537>

Look for these author notes throughout. They provide research development (RD) insights and best practices to help you submit a successful proposal/application.

THE CHALLENGE OF FINDING FUNDING

Why searching for funding opportunities is important.

Searching for funding opportunities is essential for most researchers, as support from federal, foundation, and corporate funders can enable them to pursue projects and access resources that may not be possible with the limited internal research funding available at many institutions of higher education. While the amount of funding required to perform research varies across disciplines, regardless of the funding needs of the researcher, obtaining external funding will help them achieve their research goals and support their career advancement. Additionally, applying for grant funding is a competitive process, and being awarded a research grant is a sign of excellence in your field. Some examples of the ways researchers use grant funding to support their work include:

- **Support for salary and wages** (e.g., course buy-outs, sabbaticals, summer salary, team members' salaries, support for research assistants including students, postdocs, and staff)
- **Support for equipment** (e.g., research-related equipment that costs \$5,000 or more and has a useful life of greater than one year)
- **Support for travel** (e.g., professional meetings and conferences, community meetings, archive visits, travel to meet with other researchers or use research facilities)
- **Participant support costs** (e.g., support the costs of participants in conferences, meetings, symposia, training activities and workshops)
- **Support for other research costs** (e.g., materials and supplies, consultant services, honoraria for speakers, translations or other services, publishing and dissemination costs, computer services, etc.)

What makes searching for funding opportunities difficult?

Insufficient Time & Consistency - Everyone involved in research—whether they are faculty members, trainees, or research development professionals—is often pressed for time. As a result, even people who are eager to learn about new funding opportunities are often not consistently searching for them. However, inconsistency in searching for funding can lead to missed chances or to not learning about promising funding opportunities until it is too late to put together a strong application. Because many funding opportunities have short application windows, people risk missing them if they are not actively and consistently **looking**.

When funding mechanisms are new, fewer people tend to know about them and apply, which makes them less competitive. Being one of the first people to spot an opportunity will give you a competitive advantage. However, we've also learned that funding cycles that repeat within the same fiscal year tend to be more competitive earlier compared to later in the fiscal year.

Another common challenge researchers face when they begin searching for funding is underestimating the time needed to identify promising funding opportunities. Developing an effective search strategy goes beyond just entering keywords into a search tool—it requires planning. This article will discuss why planning is important and how it saves time in the long run.

Lack of Knowledge of Resources - Researchers who are new to an institution, or who are new to searching for grant funding, may not be familiar with the resources available to help them find funding opportunities. Additionally, researchers who are branching into a new area of research may not yet be familiar with the funding landscape in their new area of research. Learning about the resources available to you and becoming familiar with the funding landscape in your field are key steps to support your funding success. Gaining this knowledge will streamline your approach to searching for funding and allow you to strategically plan ahead for when you will pursue specific funding opportunities to support your research and creative pursuits.

At many institutions, staff members such as research development (RD) professionals, research administrators, or those in the office of sponsored programs, assist researchers with finding funding opportunities as a core part of their jobs. More than 70% of RD professionals help to find and distribute funding. https://nordp.memberclicks.net/assets/NORD/Eck_Roney_WhatsRD_.pdf

Unmet Expectations - Another major challenge in searching for funding opportunities is that the process frequently does not align with researchers' expectations. An effective search involves more than entering a few keywords into a search engine. Many researchers experience frustration because they either find too few opportunities they think are relevant, or they find an overwhelming number of possibilities and the task of narrowing down their search results to the right fit becomes daunting. This article will help you learn effective strategies for searching so you can find a reasonable pool of funding opportunities to consider. Ref 1 can help you learn effective strategies for determining which opportunities are the best fit for your particular research project.

It is common to feel overwhelmed when you first start searching for funding opportunities. Don't worry! It gets easier over time.

Lack of familiarity with funders and standing programs - The world of funding programs has its own language, practices, and cadence. Understanding RFAs vs. NOFOs vs. BAAs, grants vs. cooperative

It's normal for some researchers to secure funding from one "home base funder" again and again over the course of their career, while others will secure funding for a single research agenda from multiple sources. Both approaches are reasonable.

agreements, activity codes, indirect cost return rates, and more takes time and experience. When searching for funding opportunities, it's important to understand these terms to know if a funding opportunity is right for you or if you are even eligible to apply. As you gain more experience applying for grants and familiarity with specific funders, this will become foundational working knowledge that will allow you to quickly assess your search results. Note that at the time of this article's publication, many federal funders are rapidly changing their programs and funding priorities. It is important for investigators to stay up to date about funders' current priorities as they search for new funding opportunities that align with their research, scholarship, and creative artistry

You don't have to do this alone! Reach out to research development or administration staff at your institution for support or to mentors with experience grant writing.

Beyond understanding the jargon, it can be challenging at first to understand how a given research project fits within the national research landscape and aligns with research priorities at the funding agencies.

Table 1 in Section 3 in the Proposed Solutions and Implementation Section below includes information on the missions or priorities of major federal grant-awarding agencies. These missions illustrate how the federal funding agencies define their research scope – while avoiding overlap – and can guide where you should look for funding opportunities. For example, if you are conducting research in microbiology with clear applications to human health, your research could be a good fit for an NIH award. However, if this exact same research is presented as a way to advance fundamental understanding in biology, it would be a better fit at NSF. The mission statements and priorities statements of the institute, directorate, or program administering a funding opportunity can also provide insight as to whether your search is on the right track. Ref. 1 explores in more detail how to best assess fit for a funding opportunity.

Finally, each funding agency has its own processes, procedures, and culture. Several agencies run standing programs in addition to putting out new solicitations that align with current funding priorities. In some cases, standing programs may only be minimally advertised, or not advertised at all, because the funding opportunity runs on the same cycle year-to-year. Or, with many foundations, an announcement that the foundation's annual funding cycle is open is sent to the main contact at a university, who then must distribute it internally. For new researchers, these processes can make it challenging to find these kinds of opportunities. Gaining familiarity with the funding landscape helps, but this takes time and effort.

Reach out to support on campus – research development professionals, research administrators, Foundation Relations, Advancement, etc. – if you need help navigating a new agency and understanding what opportunities may exist that are not well-advertised.

How will this article help you?

Many resources are available to help researchers identify funding opportunities to support their research and creative pursuits. This article will help you become familiar with current resources for searching for funding opportunities and strategies to optimize the use of these

resources. While many of the resources available to aid your funding search will vary across institutions, regardless of which resources are available to you, taking time to become familiar with these resources will help you identify funders and track funding opportunities in a timely manner. This article will help you establish a strong routine that leverages multiple resources to search for funding, and lead you through best practices for developing a plan to guide your searches. Planning ahead will help you identify funding opportunities to support not just a single project, but also the trajectory of your research program over the long run.

PROPOSED SOLUTIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION

Although many things can be easily found through a Google search, funding opportunities are (usually) not one of them (n.b., funding opportunities are not available in Google Scholar). Most of the subscription-based search engines that are specifically designed for funding opportunities are expensive and, therefore, not accessible to everyone. While free funding opportunity databases are available, especially for federal sponsors, these free options are often more difficult to use than pay-to-play options. In general, if you want to conduct a thorough search for opportunities so you can find your best funding fit (Ref 1), you will need to use multiple tools.

There is also a bit of skill involved in learning to rapidly perform an effective funding opportunity search. Ideally, when performing a keyword search, you want to get about a dozen good options that you can quickly view to identify a few promising results. More often, one of two things happen: you get very few results (or maybe even no results!) or you get hundreds of results, which are too many to manually read through. Having a strategy for how you will expand or restrict your search is important.

Knowing what you are hoping to find in advance can be helpful, but that usually means you have searched before and/or you have some idea about the funding landscape. This is why seasoned research development professionals are generally better at finding funding opportunities than new tenure-track faculty. Good news! This article is intended to help you build the skills you need to find funding opportunities like a pro.

How do I prepare to search for funding?

Build a roadmap for your research. Before you start searching for funding opportunities, thinking critically about your personal and professional goals will inform your search.

- 1. Self-reflect before you dive into searching.** It is critical that you figure out where you want to go, not just with this grant, but with the next one, and the one after that. Consider questions like:
 - “What do I want to do, and why do I want to do it?”
 - “What do I want my research program to look like in five years?”
 - “Who will my research positively impact?”
 - “Who will be interested in my work?”
 - “How much money do I need?”
 - “How will each award help build a ladder to the next one?”
 - “Do I qualify for any ‘special category’ grants, e.g., early career, MSI-only opportunities, etc.?”
 - “Who in my network can I look to for ideas about how to fund my research?”

Your particular research program and career path may include these questions, or others. Also, review your own prior work and look at how you’ve positioned the literature gap so that you can get a better idea of where you are going with your research.

- 2. Seek guidance from others.** Talk to your mentors, including tenured faculty at your institution and your department chair, about your research roadmap. Expectations about extramural funding vary widely between institutions, between departments within the same institution, and even between faculty within the same department, depending on the terms of their faculty contract. This is why it’s so important to make sure your roadmap aligns with senior faculty’s expectations of you; they will be evaluating your portfolio. Checking in with other early career faculty who are senior to you at your institution and who are on track to obtain tenure can be especially helpful, because they are the most likely to have similar expectations. Also seek feedback from mentors in your field who have successfully received funding for their research and creative pursuits. These mentors can help you develop a strategy for when and how often to seek funding opportunities and write grant applications. Librarians may also be able to help you hone your keywords or disciplinary trends, so consider reaching out to them, too. Think outside the box and use all your resources!

- 3. Write it down!** Whether you prefer an outline, a concept map, or a Gantt chart, there really is no right or wrong way to do this. Putting your plans onto paper helps you organize your thoughts, identify additional resources you may need, see potential pitfalls and opportunities, and it holds you accountable to taking action. Start with your major goals and work backwards to the individual steps you'll need to take to achieve them. We recommend making a long-term plan with more general goals, and then a detailed plan for the next semester or two. If your institution has a subscription to NCFDD, a leading provider of professional development resources for faculty, check out the webinar, *Every Semester Needs a Plan*. It can help you do this

Develop and regularly revisit your roadmap, thinking of it as a 'living document' that helps you keep track of where you want to go and what kind of funding will be necessary to reach your goals. By considering these questions up front, it can be easier to identify keywords to use in your searches, what types of grants may be the best fit for your project, and whether your team has the collaborators and resources ready to be competitive for your next grant application. While developing a roadmap will be a time commitment up front, going through this process will help you more easily identify relevant opportunities and submit more competitive proposals.

How do I get started searching for funding?

- 1. Get advice from others.** At your institution, there may be administrators, staff, and faculty who frequently run funding searches as part of their job duties. This includes research development professionals, research administrators, government relations staff, advancement staff, research deans, and other colleagues or mentors. For government funding, your government relations team can provide important insight into a sponsor's priorities and program goals (see Refs 1 & 2 for more information about finding an appropriate funding fit and positioning your project).
- 2. Learn about sponsors and their funding priorities.** Spend some time researching different sponsors that may have relevant opportunities in your research area, including all levels of government (federal, state, and local), foundations, and industry sponsors. Learn about their mission and current priorities to best understand if your research aligns with their interests, and how your proposal can be framed to be the most competitive (Ref 2). For government sponsors, your government relations and research development groups can be valuable resources for expert insight. **Table 1** below provides the mission statements for several common federal funders. While specific priorities may vary depending on current national concerns, these mission statements underpin their priorities over time.

Seek advice from colleagues, especially those in related fields, to learn who's funding their work. Check databases like NIH RePORTER or read acknowledgments in publications to spot potential funders. A quick coffee chat can yield creative funding ideas and point you to sponsors you may not have considered.

If you are interested in opportunities from foundations or industry sponsors, reach out to your foundation relations, corporate engagement, or development/advancement teams, if those groups are available at your institution. Unlike government funding, funding from foundations and industry are often built on personal relationships. These teams at your institution are very likely to have existing relationships with these sponsors, or at least contacts there. We strongly encourage you to reach out to your foundation relations and/or corporate engagement team(s) first if you are considering applying for funding from a foundation or industry partner. These internal teams can provide valuable insight into the sponsor’s priorities and preferences and help facilitate conversations with program officers or decision makers.

TABLE 1. Missions of Major Federal Funders*

Agency	Mission Statement
Department of Agriculture (USDA)	To provide leadership on food, agriculture, natural resources, rural development, nutrition, and related issues based on public policy, the best available science, and effective management.
Department of Defense (DOD)	To provide the military forces needed to deter war and to protect the security of the United States.
Department of Education (DOE)	To promote student achievement and preparation for global competitiveness by fostering educational excellence and ensuring equal access.
Department of Energy (DOE)	To ensure America’s security and prosperity by addressing its energy, environmental and nuclear challenges through transformative science and technology solutions.
National Aerospace and Space Administration (NASA)	To explore the unknown in air and space, innovate for the benefit of humanity, and inspire the world through discovery.
National Endowment for the Arts (NEA)	To provide funding for the arts and arts education in communities nationwide and serve as a catalyst of public and private support for the arts.
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH)	To serve and strengthen our nation by supporting high-quality projects and programs in the humanities and by making the humanities available to all Americans.
National Institutes of Health (NIH)	To seek fundamental knowledge about the nature and behavior of living systems and the application of that knowledge to enhance health, lengthen life, and reduce illness and disability.
National Institute of Justice (NIJ)	To foster and disseminate knowledge and tools derived from objective and rigorous scientific research to inform efforts that promote safety and advance justice.
National Science Foundation (NSF)	To promote the progress of science; to advance the national health, prosperity and welfare; and to secure the national defense.

*At the time of this publication, these are advertised missions on the agencies’ websites. The authors recognize that the missions are evolving in 2025.

3. Learn about the resources available to you to help you find funding.

Many organizations pay for subscriptions to funding opportunity search engines such as Pivot or GrantForward. Check with your research office, your advancement office, and your library, because any one of these units might have tools available. In particular, advancement offices frequently have access to search engines that are optimized for foundation opportunities (e.g., Candid or Instrumentl).

If you don't have institutional funding search programs, there are open-access tools available. Grants.gov and SAM.gov allow you to broadly scan most federal funding opportunities. SAM.gov is especially helpful for broad agency announcements or BAAs, which tend to be used by the Department of Defense and agencies like APRA. Grantmakers.io will help you identify organizations with 990 tax forms, so you can get a sense of the foundations that offer funding opportunities. Note that search tools are also available on specific federal sponsor websites, and these tools are often easier to use than broader, open-access databases. Links to the websites of some federal funders are included in the Resources at the end of this article. Also, don't forget to search for local funding opportunities on the websites of state and city governments.

Table 2. Summary of Funding Opportunity Search Engines

Product	Open access?	Funders OR Funders & Opps	Types of Funders	Save keywords?	Create a profile?	Sends alerts?
Academic Analytics	no	Funders & Opportunities	All types	yes	yes	yes
Candid	no	Funders	Non-profits	no	no	no
GrantForward	no	Funders & Opportunities	All types	yes	yes	yes
Grantmakers.io	yes	Funders	Non-profits	no	no	no
Grants.gov	yes	Funders & Opportunities	Federal funders	no	yes	yes
Instrumentl	no	Funders & Opportunities	All types	yes	no	no
Pivot	no	Funders & Opportunities	All types	yes	yes	yes
SAM.gov	yes	Funders & Opportunities	Federal funders		yes	

4. **Seek resources at nearby institutions.** In addition to using open-access search tools, consider visiting a nearby institution that has the tools you want to use. Often, funding search engines can be accessed at the libraries of more research-active institutions. You might be able to walk into those libraries and use their services. If that is not an option, consider contacting a colleague at that institution who is in a similar role as you and ask if they are willing to help you gain access. Engaging with a colleague at a neighboring institution could even foster a potential collaboration.
5. **Ask for the resources you need.** You should also consider asking your institution to purchase a subscription to a funding opportunity search engine if they don't already have one. While subscriptions to these search engines can be expensive, the return on investment might be high if there is enough demand for the tool at your institution. Work with a research development professional or a research administrator at your institution to help you make your case.
6. **Set up your searches.** An ideal search will return approximately 10-20 results. Some broad searches – especially in popular research areas – can return hundreds of results. Or, if your search is too constrained, you may receive very few – or no – results. You need to answer questions like the ones listed under #1 "[Self-reflect before you dive into searching](#)" (above) so that you can most easily identify opportunities that are a good fit for you. An early career faculty member may be interested in pursuing an award that can be used as a stepping stone for a center grant, while a tenured full professor may not need those options. For a full discussion of these considerations, please see the EMERGE article "Is This the Right Fit? Evaluating Funding Opportunities for Your Research" (1).

There's a reason we listed this last. It's because we want you to do the things listed above BEFORE you start searching. It'll make your search go more smoothly. Also, we highly recommend working with your research development or library staff to learn how to do this for the specific subscription database(s) you have access to at your institution.

How do I maintain my funding opportunity searches?

1. **Save searches and/or set up keyword alerts** so you know when relevant opportunities are posted. Many of the products available for finding funding opportunities allow you to save searches and/or set up keyword alerts. Saved searches allow you to manually re-run a search with set parameters and filters.

Keyword alerts send you a notification (usually an email) when a relevant opportunity is available. Take advantage of these features! Regardless of the system or product, it will likely be more work than you initially anticipate to set up searches that return results that are relevant to your research project (see #3 under "[Learn about the resources available to you to help you find funding](#)," above). However, these features greatly simplify the searching process and help ensure that you don't miss opportunities.

Be open to diverse funding sources—including foundations, state and local governments, and corporate funders—not just national agencies. Opportunities can come from unexpected places, so use varied keywords in your searches and consider the different audiences your work may impact.

2. **Sign up for newsletters** from funding agencies. Are there sponsors from which you regularly pursue funding opportunities? Do you find yourself returning again and again to grants from one NSF directorate or a particular foundation? Newsletters from these sponsors are one of the best ways to get the most up-to-date information. They arrive directly to your inbox without you having to search. You can tailor the newsletters to your interest and (to a large extent) control the number you receive. We all deal with a lot of email, so the key, of course, is keeping an eye out for these newsletters and then actually reading them to find the opportunities. Links to sign up for newsletters from federal funders are included in the Resources section at the end of this article.

Also, find out if any units within your institution publish newsletters with funding opportunities. If they do, join their mailing list! These lists should be curated to only include opportunities your institution is eligible for. It's also likely that these opportunities will be ones that your institution is especially well-suited for..

What are my next steps?

1. **Keep looking for funding opportunities! Set up a regular schedule to search for funding opportunities.** Set aside time every month to search for new opportunities. We recommend routinely searching for at least 30 minutes each week, but this can vary depending on your needs. Set up a recurring appointment in your calendar so you don't forget!
2. **Assess the fit of your project for the funding opportunities you've found.** See Ref 1.
3. **Position yourself to be competitive for the opportunity.**
4. **Revisit your roadmap.** Schedule a 30-min meeting with yourself a few times per year to reflect on the roadmap you've created and decide if it is still the path you want to pursue. This is a great thing to do between semesters, when you are reflecting on how your past semester went and preparing for the next one to begin.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This article is intended to help researchers learn how to establish a successful routine for identifying funding opportunities. By learning the following skills, you will be in a strong position to identify funders who may be interested in funding your work, as well as new funding opportunities that align with your work.

- **Establish a roadmap** for your research and creative pursuits. Revisit and update this roadmap on a regular basis to make sure you know what projects to focus on seeking funding for, and to develop a timeline for seeking and applying for funding.
- **Consider all of your resources.** Be familiar with the search tools that are available to you online and at your institution. Also, consider the resources that are available to you through your scholarly network to help you identify funders.
- **Develop a routine for searching for funding opportunities.** Set aside time in your schedule each month to search for funding opportunities. (Make an appointment on your calendar!)
- **Sign up for email alerts** to find out when a new funding opportunity is posted that matches your research interests. These tools simplify the process of searching for funding opportunities, and help you maximize the amount of time you have available to prepare a grant application.
- **Sign up for newsletters from funding agencies** to receive up-to-date information about funding opportunities.
- **Be open to unfamiliar funding opportunities.** Promising funding opportunities can arise from unexpected sources.

RESOURCES

- NEA: [Grants](#)
- NEH: [Grants Search | National Endowment for the Humanities](#)
- NIH Matchmaker: [RePORT > RePORTER](#)
[NIH Funding Announcements](#)
- NIH: [Funding | Grants & Funding](#)
- NSF: [Funding Search | NSF - National Science Foundation](#)
[NSF Announcements](#)
- USDA: [Search all competitive Request for Applications \(RFAs\)](#)
- NASA: [ROSES \(Research Opportunities in Space and Earth Sciences\)](#)
- DOE: [Grant.gov Department of Energy \(DOE\)](#)
[DOE Announcements](#)
- NIJ: [Current Funding Opportunities](#)
- DOD:..... [ARL Funding](#)
[ONR Funding Announcements](#)
[ARFL Funding Opportunities](#)
[DARPA Funding Opportunities](#)

AUTHORS

Lauren Aerni-Flessner, PhD, MBA

Research Development Specialist, Michigan State University

Lauren Aerni-Flessner is a Research Development Specialist in the Office of Research & Innovation at Michigan State University. In this role, she helps faculty prepare competitive grant proposals through editing, consultations, and pre-submission reviews. She also leads cohort-based grant writing programs for MSU faculty and organizes professional development seminars on grant-related topics, including identifying funding opportunities. Lauren holds a PhD in molecular cell biology from Washington University in St. Louis and an MBA from the University of Michigan.

Heather Abbott, PhD

Director of Research Development and Professor of Chemistry,
Kennesaw State University

Heather Abbott leads research development efforts at Kennesaw State University, supporting faculty in identifying funding opportunities, strengthening proposals, and building interdisciplinary collaborations. A physical chemist by training, she brings over 15 years of research and academic experience to her role, combining scientific expertise with a strategic focus on advancing KSU's research enterprise.

Rachel Wallace, PhD

Assistant Vice President for Research Enhancement and Development,
Wayne State University

Rachel Wallace serves as the Assistant Vice President for Research Development at Wayne State University. In this role, she leads initiatives to enhance the university's research enterprise by supporting faculty in securing external funding, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations, and developing strategic resources for proposal development. Under her leadership, the Research Development team has supported faculty in developing major large-scale, interdisciplinary proposals and training grants. Rachel holds a PhD in Chemistry from the University of Michigan.

REFERENCES

Spires, M, and Wright, G. (2025). Is This the Right Fit? Evaluating Funding Opportunities for Your Research. The NORDP Consultants Program. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16540376>

Wright, G., and Spires, M. (2025). Reaching Out: Best Practices for Contacting Program Officers. The NORDP Consultants Program. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16540189>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors thank the New Opportunities for Research Development Committee of the National Organization of Research Development Professionals, who critically read earlier versions of this resource and offered substantive feedback.

National Organization of Research Development Consultants Program (NORDP)

Expanding MSI and ERI Research Capacity and Competitiveness

www.nordp.org